

Evaluation of amino acids for their radioprotective efficacy by analytical techniques^ψ

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Under two dose rates of 1.16 Gy/s and 0.008 Gy/s, R_f values of 5-hydroxy-L-tryptophan, L-cysteine and cystamine were determined at physiological pH of 6.4–6.5. 5-Hydroxy-L-tryptophan showed consistent decrease in R_f value with increase in dose but not with dose rate and L-cysteine showed increase in R_f value with dose especially at lower dose rate compared to that at higher dose rate, whereas cystamine showed no change in R_f value with increase in dose as well as change in dose rate.

During gamma irradiation, L-cysteine showed positive and cystamine showed negative test for desulphuration, L-cysteine and 5-hydroxy-L-tryptophan showed positive test for decarboxylation. All the amino acids showed positive test for deamination with radiation dose. This has been quantified as a function of dose. Decarboxylation, deamination and desulphuration from respective amino acids have been confirmed by IR spectroscopy.

Number of ammonia molecules liberated per μ mole for a dose of 100 Gy was in the order of 5-hydroxy-L-tryptophan > L-cysteine > cystamine. The radioprotective efficacy as governed by proton acceptance by $-NH_2$ groups will be in the same order.

Depletion of $-SH$, $-NH_2$ and $-COOH$ depends on total dose, dose rate and bond energies of these functional groups. All these determine radioprotective efficacy of selected amino acids.

Paper chromatographic studies have been reported for 5-hydroxy-L-tryptophan (5HTP), cystamine and L-cysteine as these are connected with metabolism¹, body fluids², urine³, blood serum⁴ etc. As amino acids are well known radioprotectors and under normal and radiation-induced conditions the amounts of amino acids varied. But it is possible to detect these amino acids by this inexpensive technique. By using this technique some important proteins have also been detected by us⁵, the detection limit was ~20–25 μ g/ml.

IR spectral studies on 5-hydroxy-L-tryptophan has been reported⁶ and by using this technique detection limit for amino acids can be lowered. Moreover, subtle structural alterations in the amino acids as a result of gamma irradiation can be detected by IR spectroscopy. As radioprotection is vitally dependent upon amino acids, the effect of dose rate on their structural alterations have been reported by us recently⁷.

The radioprotective efficacy of 5HTP, cystamine and L-cysteine is determined by using their dose reduction factors

(DRF). The DRF values are 1.3 for 5HTP⁸, 1.65 for cystamine⁹ and 1.8 for L-cysteine¹⁰. The DRF value of a radioprotector is connected with its functional groups and structural alteration in the unirradiated and gamma irradiated states. The present study has been designed to explore the effects of radiation dose on functional groups ($-COOH$, $-SH$ and $-NH_2$) present in the amino acids and the possible relationship for radioprotective efficacy.

Results and discussion

Table 1 shows the R_f values of 5HTP, L-cysteine and cystamine as a function of gamma radiation dose at the dose rates of 1.16 and 0.008 Gy/s up to a maximum dose of 200 Gy. For 5HTP, R_f values consistently decreased with increase in dose, but no dose rate effect was observed. This indicates depletion of polar groups (i.e. $COOH$ and $-NH_2$) with dose. This technique is relatively insensitive compared to absorbance⁷. L-Cysteine showed little increase in R_f value at higher dose rate, but at lower dose rate comparatively higher values were obtained. This may be due to accumulation of counterions and pulling effect of water produced radicals

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Table 1. R_f values of 5-hydroxy-L-tryptophan, L-cysteine and cystamine as a function of gamma irradiation dose at two dose rates pH 6.4–6.5

Dose rate 1.16 Gy/s					
5-Hydroxy-L-tryptophan		L-Cysteine		Cystamine	
25 μ M		100 mM		100 mM	
Dose (Gy)	R_f	Dose (Gy)	R_f	Dose (Gy)	R_f
Unirr.	0.78	Unirr.	0.37	Unirr.	0.35
30	0.61	30	0.37	50	0.37
50	0.58	50	0.38	100	0.38
100	0.49	100	0.40	200	0.39
200	0.32	200	0.43		
Dose Rate 0.008 Gy/s					
Unirr.	0.78	Unirr.	0.37	Unirr.	0.35
30	0.63	30	0.49	50	0.40
50	0.68	50	0.54	100	0.40
100	0.50	100	0.56	200	0.40

S.D. = ± 0.005 (max) for a dose rate of 1.16 Gy/s and S.D. = ± 0.007 (max) for a dose rate of 0.008 Gy/s; $n = 3$.

towards -SH, -NH₂ and -COOH groups especially at higher dose rate. The effect on dose rate induced absorbance change has been reported by us⁷. Cystamine hardly showed any variation in R_f value with dose at both the dose rates up to 200 Gy. Radioresistant nature of cystamine has also been reported by us⁷. The structure of the molecule has a disulfide bond. Intermolecular cross linking is favourable for making the compound radioresistant. In the total dose range these amino acids may produce certain radiolytic transient intermediates. But the final probable neutral compounds of 5HTP, L-cysteine and cystamine are 5-hydroxyindole, ethane and hexane respectively.

IR spectroscopy¹¹ of these amino acids (Table 2) revealed: (a) decarboxylation and deamination from 5HTP with increasing radiation dose and no intermolecular hydrogen bond formation between OH groups, (b) COOH vibration has increased with dose, NH₃ deformation and NH stretching mode alongwith C-S stretching vibration increased for L-cysteine and (c) for cystamine there were minute changes up to 20 Gy. So the compound is radioresistant.

The IR studies have been further confirmed by using spot tests for the compounds. The nature of complex formed between an amino acid and ninhydrin for purple pigment formation as determined by paper chromatography is well reported¹².

It has been observed that Nessler's reagent and its complex¹³ with ammonia showed a λ_{max} at 225 nm. There was a linear increase in the absorbance at $A_{225\text{ nm}}$ when plotted against $10-50 \times 10^{-7}\%$ of ammonia complexed with

Table 2. Infra-red spectral characteristics of L-cysteine and 5-hydroxy-L-tryptophan and cystamine

L-Cysteine = 0.4 mM; cystamine = 100 mM. Dose rate = 1.16 Gy/s; solvent-water

Dose (Gy)	ν_{max}	Assignment
Unirr.		Increase in NH stretching vibration with dose
20	3517	
40		
80		
100	1650	NH ₃ deformation and COOH vibration have increased with dose
200		
	700	C-S stretching vibration has increased with dose
		5-Hydroxy-L-tryptophan
Unirr.		
50	3685–3690	Phenolic OH group free.
100		No hydrogen bond formation
200	1650–1750	NH ₃ deformation (asym).
300		Decarboxylation from COOH group with dose
500		Increase in rocking frequency intensity with dose
		Cystamine
Unirr.		
2	700	C-S stretching vibration has decreased with dose
5	1625	NH deformation mode intensity has decreased with dose
10		
20	3415	NH stretching vibration intensity has decreased with dose

$n = 3$.

Nessler's reagent. This calibration curve ($r = 0.99$) and its extrapolation has been used for complex formation with Nessler's reagent. The amount of ammonia liberated from 5HTP, L-cysteine and cystamine as a function of total dose of irradiation have been presented in Table 3.

The liberation of ammonia is fast up to 100 Gy for 5HTP (25 μ M), beyond which it has leveled. Ammonia liberation was steady upto 100 Gy for L-cysteine, beyond which it has leveled. The liberation of ammonia with dose for cystamine (1 mM) is very slow up to 200 Gy and at 300 Gy it has increased. This led to the conclusion that number of ammo-

Table 3. Amount of ammonia liberated from L-cysteine, cystamine and 5-hydroxy-L-tryptophan as a function of dose of gamma irradiation
Dose rate 1.16 Gy/s

L-Cysteine = 0.008 mM (λ_{\max} 226 nm)			Cystamine = 1 mM (λ_{\max} 230 nm)			5-Hydroxy-L-tryptophan (25 μ M) (λ_{\max} 225 nm)		
Dose (Gy)	$\Delta A_{\lambda_{\max}}$	Amount of ammonia liberated $\times 10^{-7} M$	Dose (Gy)	$\Delta A_{\lambda_{\max}}$	Amount of ammonia liberated $\times 10^{-7} M$	Dose (Gy)	$\Delta A_{\lambda_{\max}}$	Amount of ammonia liberated $\times 10^{-7} M$
Unirr.	–	–	Unirr.	–	–	Unirr.	–	–
20	0.07	1.335	20	0.22	6.408	20	0.15	0.634
40	0.19	5.340	40	0.26	14.950	60	0.20	6.620
60	0.25	13.350	60	0.42	16.020	80	0.35	29.370
80	0.72	24.030	100	0.46	17.180	100	0.79	37.380
100	1.01	42.720	200	0.58	19.760	200	0.90	40.050
200	1.03	43.790	300	0.72	30.970	300	0.98	42.180

$n = 3$; Maximum variation in standard deviation in $\Delta A_{\lambda_{\max}}$ value was ± 0.01 .

nia molecules liberated for a dose of 100 Gy was in the order of 5HTP > L-cysteine > cystamine. So NH_2 groups are depleted in same decreasing order of preference for the same dose. In aqueous medium, on radiolysis protons will be accepted in the order of 5HTP > L-cysteine > cystamine. The radioprotective efficacy as governed by proton acceptance by NH_2 groups will be accordingly possible.

Experimental

The amino acids, 5-hydroxy-L-tryptophan, cystamine, L-cysteine – all were procured from Sigma. Chemicals of A.R. grade acetone, butanol, acetic acid, sodium carbonate, potassium ferrocyanide, ninhydrin, Nessler's reagent, zinc sulphate, sodium nitroprusside, phenolphthalein and sodium hydroxide were obtained from E. Merck. Tripple-distilled water and Whatman paper No. 1 were used for the experiment.

Absorbance measurements were done by GBC, UV-visible spectrophotometer (Model 916) of accuracy ± 0.001 absorbance unit. Gamma irradiation for a higher dose rate was done in Gamma Chamber 5000 (BRIT, Mumbai) and for lower dose rate Gamma Cell 220 (Model GC 220) of Atomic Energy of Canada Limited was used. pH measurements were done in Toshniwal pH meter (Model CL 46) of accuracy ± 0.01 unit. FT-IR (BIO-RAD, U.S.A., Model FTS 40) equipment was used for taking IR spectra of gamma irradiated solutions of amino acids were taken. Gamma irradiation of the solutions of amino acids were determined by FBX¹⁴ and Fricke dosimetry¹⁵.

Detection and quantitation of ammonia was done by mixing the amino acids in their respective concentrations

with Nessler's reagent and were irradiated at a dose rate of 1.16 Gy/s up to a maximum dose of 500 Gy. A purple colour has been developed after thorough stirring and heating to a temperature of $40 \pm 0.1^\circ$ for half an hour in an air oven. L-Cysteine (0.008 mM), cystamine (1 mM) and 5-hydroxy-L-tryptophan (25 μ M) showed absorption maxima at 226, 230 and 225 nm respectively in the unirradiated and differently gamma irradiated states. Amount of ammonia liberated from these amino acids as a result of gamma irradiation could be quantified by a calibration curve as is developed by Nessler's reagent, by plotting $A_{225 \text{ nm}}$ versus concentration of ammonia.

For each amino acid for a particular dose, number of ammonia molecules liberated was calculated as : number of molecules of ammonia liberated for a particular dose = $NM/\text{Dose (Gy)}$ where N = Avogadro's number = 6.023×10^{23} ; M = number of moles of ammonia liberated. 1 Gy = 3.6×10^{14} eV.

Detection of sulfur-dioxide was done for L-cysteine (100 mM) and cystamine (100 mM) by irradiating them up to a dose of 500 Gy at a dose rate of 1.16 Gy/s by a spot test. One drop of test solution is mixed with 1 drop of 1(N) $\text{K}_4(\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6)$, 1 drop of ZnSO_4 solution and 1 drop of 1% sodium nitroprusside solution. That produced red colour, indicating the formation of sulphur dioxide. L-Cysteine showed positive test for sulphur dioxide whereas cystamine did not respond to this test.

Detection of carbon dioxide was tested with 0.5 ml irradiated (dose 200 Gy) solutions of L-cysteine (100 mM) and 5HTP (25 μ M). Phenolphthalein was colourised with 2%

sodium carbonate and 0.1 (N) sodium hydroxide. One drop of this coloured solution was diluted to 2 ml with distilled water. Add 0.5 ml irradiated solutions as mentioned. Decolourisation took place with both 5HTP and L-cysteine. IR spectra of unirradiated and irradiated (dose rate 1.16 Gy/s) solutions were taken. Three replicate observations were performed for all the experiments.

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